

ANALYSIS OF FEASIBILITY OF USING CARBON FIBER AND EPOXY RESIN TO CONNECTION NODES OF WOODEN TRUSSES

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ABSTRACT

In this study was carried out a physical experimentation of a joint of wooden structure made of carbon fiber with epoxy resin. The aim was to evaluate the nodal displacement and the making procedure. The obtained results demonstrated the viability of the technique of making wooden joints with carbon fiber and allowed obtaining the rotational stiffness coefficient. This coefficient can be used to adjust the boundary conditions of truss members to that they behavior as a semi-rigid connection, allowing to evaluate the structural displacements relation to the Serviceability Limit State (SLS) in a more realistic condition.

KEYWORDS

Carbon Fiber; Epoxy Resin; Wood; Connections; Truss.

INTRODUCTION

Eucalyptus wood is widely used in the timber industry, and, for this reason, it is a valuable natural resource. According to Amer et al. (2022), eucalyptus is characterized by its rapid growth, which makes it cultivated in several regions of the world to supply the growing demand for wood. Particurlaly, the species of Eucalyptus cloeziana is native to Australia, and its cultivation in other countries takes place through seeds (seedlings).

According to Cunha et al. (2014), the first eucalyptus plantations in Brazil began in the 20th century, but materials derived from this type of wood only started to be used in civil construction much later. Cunha et al. (2014) state that eucalyptus production in planted forests resulted from actions taken to reduce the exploitation of natural resources in native forests in Brazil. It was believed that the adoption of eucalyptus extracted from reforestation areas would give construction projects sustainability characteristics, which has promoted an expansion of the use of eucalyptus from reforestation in the civil construction market.

According to Cunha et al. (2014), research related to the physical and mechanical characterization of species of the Eucalyptus genus in Brazil, allowed the use of this material for structural purposes, as it has a good mechanical strength/density ratio. Eucalyptus can reach maturity between 10 and 20 years, considered a short period compared to other genres. With favorable physical and mechanical properties, this type of wood gives constructions durability and mechanical resistance. From an aesthetic point of view, it presents attractive appeals, with varied shades, ranging from light to dark.

Buildings in general, including those made of wood, are susceptible to damage and wear and tear arising from the executive process, design flaws, or as a result of increased load due to change of use of the enterprise or due to wear and tear with the use of the building itself. From this perspective, the influence of environmental factors on the acceleration of wear in construction materials can be seen. According to studies by Nappi et al. (2013), the use of metal parts in connections of wooden trusses can be quite problematic in environments with a high level of humid atmosphere, such as places close

to the sea. This occurs because the corrosion of metals leads to the opening of cracks in the wood, facilitating the entry of moisture into the material. Thus, the importance of proposing constructive alternatives for wood in these environmental conditions is highlighted, one of which may be the use of carbon fiber.

Carbon fiber is a material that adds several benefits, having found good acceptance in the civil industry. According to Callister and Rethwisch (2018), they have an advantageous ratio of modulus of elasticity and mechanical strength with their own weight. This is a material widely used in the repair of reinforced concrete structures, which has been gaining ground in many other applications, due to its high tensile strength and good thermal and chemical stability.

Carbon fiber has also been used as a method of strengthening the structure during its development, to provide more structural resistance. In this context, research related to the use of this fiber has been on the rise in recent years, as information about its performance has become indispensable for the construction market, due to the constructive importance of the material.

According to Nadir et al. (2016), fiber-reinforced polymer composites have high strength in relation to their own weight, good adaptability, are immune to corrosion and reduce maintenance costs. In this sense, from theoretical analyses, the hypothesis arises that the nodes of a wooden truss can be efficient if they are done with carbon fiber. In addition to that, the use of carbon fiber in that context, can be a feasible alternative for environments characterized by a high humidity zone and chemical aggressivity.

Due to that was exposed previously, the present study consisted of an exploratory investigation with the objective of analyzing nodes of truss made with carbon fiber and epoxy, seeking to evaluate the way of making and the displaceability of the connection. After obtaining this last aspect the structural analyzes can be performed considering the connection with some level of rotational stiffness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Moura (2003), the color of *Eucalyptus cloeziana* wood is yellowish-brown, it is resistant, with good durability, making it competitive for reforestation practices, and, when compared to other species of the *Eucalyptus* genus, it presents slow growth. Its good adaptation in Brazil is due to the similar climatic characteristics of the country with Australia, its place of origin. Araújo et al. (2004) state that the species of *Eucalyptus cloeziana* F. Muell on the north coast of Bahia, where the wood used for this research was taken, has a strategic importance for the region, due to the occupation of marginal locations and wood quality.

Souza Junior (2004) found mechanical characteristics of the species of *Eucalyptus cloeziana* from different cities in the state of Minas Gerais, in Brazil, showing little variation between the results found for the two regions, such as resistance to flexion with an approximate average value of 125 MPa, the modulus of elasticity varying approximately between 12,700 MPa and 13,130 MPa, compressive strength parallel to grain in the range of 82.5 MPa and 83.9 MPa, and shear strength close to 16 MPa and 17 MPa with the species extracted from that region. According to Alves et al. (2017), the basic density averages of *Eucalyptus cloeziana* type F. Muell wood samples aged 10 years at 12% moisture were around 703 kg/m³, 843 kg/m³, 929 kg/m³ and 916 kg /m³ for dry bulk density. With the same humidity, the apparent density varied between 10.45% and 39.16%.

Regarding carbon fiber, Pamar et al. (2015) state that, among those available on the market, this is the one with the highest rigidity among all, combining high tensile strength, favorable properties against corrosion, fagid and creep. Carbon fiber has low density and ease of processing. Pamar et al. (2015) carried out an experimental study of the mechanical properties of the bidirectional fabric of carbon fiber and obtained some of its properties under tension and flexion, with fibers oriented at different angles, and confirmed the mentioned characteristics of the material (Table 1).

Table 1: Carbon fiber bidirectional fabric properties. (Pamar et al., 2015)

In tension						
Orientation	Max. breaking load (N)	Ultimate tensile strength (N/mm ²)	Extension (mm)	Load at high yield point (N)	Young's Modulus (N/mm ²)	
90°	6,950.00	365.30	7.85	3,398.00	22,184.30	
30°	2,685.00	125.20	16.40	995.96	16,923.35	
45°	3,452.00	175.30	13.25	1,112.10	4,623.00	
In flexion						
Orientation	Max. breaking load (N)	Ultimate flexural strength (N/mm ²)	Deflection (mm)	Load at high yield point (N)	Young's Modulus (N/mm ²)	Bending Strength (3 Point) (N/mm ²)
90°	493.50	12.23	8.48	55.83	5,550.23	358.05
30°	204.30	5.87	9.84	25.32	2,456.20	175.71
45°	255.40	6.12	14.25	20.17	2,935.21	165.32

Specifically, in Jayaprakash et al. (2007) properties of the bidirectional fabric from the manufacturer Sika Company can be found (Table 2).

Table 2: Carbon fiber bidirectional fabric properties. (Jayaprakash et al., 2007)

Fiber orientation	0/90 (bidirectional)
Thickness	0.09 mm
Tensile strength	3,800 MPa
Modulus of elasticity	230,000 MPa

According to Jankowski et al. (2010), glue-wood connections tend to fail more than glue-strip connections, so the surface needs to be very well prepared before bonding, as it plays a very important role in the effectiveness of reinforcement.

One of the pioneering works in Brazil with eucalyptus and carbon fiber was that of Mohamad, Accordi and Roca (2011), with the association of composites for recovery and reinforcement of wood construction systems. These authors carried out a comparative analysis, with direct traction tests using unreinforced, in natura, autoclaved wood specimens and wooden specimens reinforced with fiberglass and carbon fiber fabrics, with bicomponent epoxy resin, and observed better performance for specimens reinforced with carbon fiber, with regard to breaking strength. In the study, they also found that glass fiber does not adhere as well with epoxy resin as carbon fiber does, which negatively interferes with its performance.

André et al. (2013) concluded that the amount of reinforcement used in wooden beams directly influences the mechanical properties of the beam, mainly the compressive strength capacity. It was observed that the compressive strength stress increased significantly with the use of CFRP. De La Rosa García et al. (2013) state that the load capacity of a beam can be increased and modified according to the properties of the material adopted for the reinforcement, depending on the type of fiber used, the way the reinforcement is distributed in the structure, the volume of polymers reinforced with fiber, and the state of the bonding surface between the wood and the FRP. This question may cover other structures as well.

De La Rosa García et al. (2013), in the analysis of reinforcement systems of composite materials, show, by carrying out experimental tests on beams without reinforcement and reinforced with basalt fiber and carbon fiber, with different weights in a U-shape, and the aid of an epoxy resin matrix forming the composite material, that the beams that had reinforcement reached higher fracture loads and greater rigidity in relation to those that did not have reinforcement. These authors found very

good results with bidirectional carbon fiber fabrics, achieving high tensions and low displacements, in addition to excelling in all parameters when compared to beams reinforced with basalt fiber fabrics. Since fiber is a material with high tensile strength, studies show a tendency for carbon fiber to be a material also indicated for techniques for strengthening deteriorated wood and with defects for the recovery of old structures, as a way to preserve the characteristics of the construction, through different reinforcement techniques. Li et al. (2014) sought to solve the problem of beams in Taiwan historical buildings deteriorated by fungi through reinforcement in the center of the wooden beam that was hollow using GFRP and CFRP rods and noted the increase in the average strength of the beams when compared to beams not reinforced.

According to studies by Pizzo and Smedley (2015), the correct application of adhesives plays a fundamental role in the efficiency of the bonded joint. The authors state that there are marked differences in the preparation of the wooden surface when done in the work environment or in the factory and emphasize that it is important to note that the control of humidity, temperature and bonding pressure in a work site is very complicated, which may impair the adhesion of the product, and this may justify the bonding thickness of the adhesives applied at the assembly site to be greater than the factory thickness.

Andor et al. (2015) performed an experimental and statistical analysis of wooden beams reinforced with unidirectional carbon fiber fabric and bicomponent epoxy resin, with different amounts of fabric layers, and different widths, and noted an increase in resistance in all reinforcement situations.

The study by Khelifa et al. (2015) demonstrated that the use of computational models presented good reliability to predict bending tests in wooden beams. These authors used finite element software to test the effect of reinforcing wooden beams with carbon fiber and concluded that reinforcement with two and three layers showed a significant increase in flexural strength compared to unreinforced beams. Furthermore, Khelifa et al. (2015) pointed out that reinforcements with composite materials contribute to increasing the stiffness of the wood with the great benefit of not having to increase the thickness of the beam, which promotes material savings and decreases the weight of the structure.

In recent years, several researchs have emerged around the reinforcement of engineered wooden structures with the use of carbon fiber. The study by Nadir et al. (2016) proved the efficiency of carbon fiber compared to fiberglass in reinforcing glulam beams, with emphasis on the double-layer configuration, as it provided better performance for the structure with increased stiffness and flexural strength.

Yang et al. (2016) studied the bending performance of glulam beams with different reinforcement techniques with CFRP bars and concluded that beams with prestressed bars with a low reinforcement rate (less than 1%) achieved an increase of more than 90% load capacity, and approximately 33% in flexural stiffness compared to unreinforced beams. They observed that bars that were not tensioned provided the structure with an increase in bending capacity of approximately 65% and bending stiffness of almost 20%.

Subhani et al. (2017) analyzed the efficiency, through three-point bending tests, of a group of rectangular beams of veneered laminated wood (LVL) without reinforcement, and with two different ways of reinforcement of CFRP, and concluded that the technique that proved to be more efficient for reinforcing the U-shaped contour of the tensioned region of the beam, as it provided a stiffness gain of 19.74% and a ductility gain of approximately 30%, in addition to providing an average load capacity increase of 25% , in relation to unreinforced beams. D'Aveni and D'Agata (2017) studied the behavior of post-stressed glulam bridges with carbon fiber cables, which provided the beam with greater beam efficiency in the ultimate limit state, and lower weight compared to structures without prestressing and of steel.

Globa et al. (2018) noticed in their studies that the technique of reinforcing LVL beams only with a strip of unidirectional fabric of CFRP with bicomponent epoxy resin presented inferior results to the

U-wrap technique, when applied in the tension region of the LVL beam, because, while the reinforcement with the external strip only increased 10% of the load capacity, 4% of ductility and 14% of rigidity, in relation to the control beams, the U-wrap technique with unidirectional fabric of CFRP, provided a gain of rigidity, ductility and load capacity by 20%, 30%, and 25%, respectively, with a more ductile fault, demonstrating much better results. Furthermore, these authors concluded that by introducing bidirectional CFRP in beam-column tests, involving the connection, very interesting results were achieved regarding the flexural strength of the CFRP-LVL composites, an increase in the load capacity of 86%, and noted that the bidirectional fabric increased the ductility of the beam, through the maximum deflection of the samples.

Rescalvo et al. (2018) carried out an experimental and analytical analysis of the bending load capacity of old wooden beams with defects, when reinforced with carbon fiber, and showed that they increased their bending load capacity by 88%, in relation to beams not reinforced. Furthermore, Rescalvo et al. (2018) state that reinforcements with metallic elements take longer, with complex installation steps, increase the weight of the structure and may lose effectiveness over time.

Bakalarz and Kossakowski (2019) performed four-point bending tests on LVL beams without reinforcement and with reinforcement of unidirectional carbon fiber fabrics with bicomponent epoxy resin, and showed that reinforcement only in the lower region of the beam was able to provide a gain of flexural strength of 30% and with the fabric surrounding the U-shaped beam up to half the height of the cross-section a gain of 35%, since it is a higher reinforcement rate. In the work of these authors, the reinforced LVL beams showed more ductility, and presented a more stable behavior, in relation to the beams without reinforcement.

Novosel et al. (2021) reinforced glue-laminated wood (glulam) beams with carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) and noted that one or two layers of fiber in the width of the beam (stress zone) provide a good ratio of mechanical properties, also reducing the maximum displacement of some. However, Novosel et al. (2021) noted that with the severe increase in layers (21 layers), the fiber tensile properties were not fully exploited due to failures in the resistance of the resin glue line with the wood. According to Bakalarz (2021), the reinforcement of engineered wood beams with CFRP strips can be indicated for structures that are already in operation, as it is easy to perform and does not require much time.

Bakalarz and Kossakowski (2022a) analyzed the performance of veneered laminated wood (LVL) beams with unidirectional CFRP fabric, with U-shaped reinforcement, through four-point bending tests and concluded that the quality of the reinforcement was superior as increased the rate of reinforcement and the surface of involvement, in addition to the fact that CFRP fabrics with epoxy resin reduces defects, it is practical, fast, and very interesting for reinforcing structures in use. Bakalarz and Kossakowski (2022b) in their studies concluded that the flexural stiffness of the beam increases according to a higher modulus of elasticity of the composite fiber, and therefore the carbon fiber fabric stands out due to its high modulus of elasticity.

As can be seen, existing studies indicate good results from the use of bidirectional carbon fiber fabric and bicomponent epoxy resin, with wooden structural parts. The predominant fabrication technique concerns the total involvement of the application region of the fiber application, in order to provide a better reinforcement area. In general, the use of U-shaped carbon fiber has shown better results than simple bonding in the form of strips. Few studies deal with the making of nodes of truss, and this gap is that was observed in the present field of research.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

It is important to mention that this study is a preliminary test, carried out with the purpose of initial, exploratory inspection, with the main objective of obtaining the displacements of a connection of round wooden pieces made with carbon fiber. Secondly, the experimentation aims to evaluate the behavior of connections of this nature, particularly, rupture modes, trends, movements, among other possible aspects to be observed. The specimen under examination consisted of a triangular prototype

made of Eucalyptus cloeziana wood, wrapped with a bidirectional 0/90 carbon fiber fabric and epoxy resin in the region of the connection between the parts.

The experiment was carried out by using a hydraulic press, manually operated, with a capacity of 133.45 kN (~15 ton-force). The wood species adopted for making the truss bars is found in Brazil, considered as having a good mechanical and workability characteristics. The wood was supplied in logs by “CM Venturoli”, taken from the reforestation area on the north coast of Bahia, Brazil, with a diameter varying between 0.06 and 0.08 meters. The Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP), adopted in the present study, was the bidirectional RC200T, provided by “Barracuda” Advanced Composites. Three layers of fabric, 50 cm long and 5 cm wide, with a thickness of 0.40 mm, were used, resulting in a fiber area of 750 cm² used in each node of the triangle. The Table 3 presents the properties indicated by the supplier for the materials used in the present experiment. Occasionally, for complementary and subsidiary purposes, Table 1 and Table 2 can be consulted.

Table 3: Properties of the used materials (“Barracuda” Advanced Composites, 2023)

Filament Resistance	240 GPa
Wire type	Carbono 3K, 33 MSI
Weft type	2/2 Twill
Weight	197 g
Thickness	0.22 mm
Yarn count	12.5 fios / 25mm

The adhesive used to glud the carbon fiber to the wood was a bicomponent epoxy resin 2001 and hardener 3154, from the manufacturer “Redelease”, used for structural purposes. The volume ratio used for epoxy resin and hardener was 2:1, as recommended by the manufacturer (Redelease, 2023). An average amount between 75 g and 90 g (g = gram) of saturant per node was used, resulting in saturation between 0.1 g/cm² and 0.12 g/cm². The total curing time of five days was respected as recommended by the manufacturer after application. Table 4 and Table 5 present the characteristics of each component and the mixture after curing.

Table 4: Component characteristics (Redelease, 2023).

Characteristics	Epoxy Resin 2001	Hardener 3154
Appearance	Colorless viscous liquid	Slightly yellowish liquid
Viscosity, 20°C, cPs	10,000 to 14,000	200 max.
Specific weight, 20°C, g/cm ³	1.16 +/- 0.01	1.005 +/- 0.015

Table 5: Mixture properties after curing (Redelease, 2023).

Thermal deflection temperature (HDT) (°C)	95-100
Compression force (MPa)	34.47
Tension force (MPa)	20.68 – 42.75
Elongation (%)	2.8

The dimensions of the prototype were defined according to the press used in the test, with a 45° angle between the lower flange and each diagonal. The triangle nodes were numbered for data collection and treatment, and together with the dimensions of the prototype can be seen in Figure 1.

The wrapping of the node followed a step-by-step process shown in Figure 2. A measuring tape was used to cut the wood and fabric. With the help of masking tape and a cardboard box as a support, it was possible to stabilize the structure for assembling the triangle. The masking tape also proved to be important in helping to cut the fabric, in the desired width, to preserve the bidirectional weave. After weighing the amount of resin and hardener on the scale, after mixing, the resin was applied to the wood with brushes in such an amount that the entire area of the fiber was saturated. Thus, with each layer of fiber, the resin was applied in the area that was filled by the fiber. The visual appearance obtained can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 1: Specimen: dimensions in meters

Figure 2: Assembly steps of the carbon fiber prototype

a) Front

b) Back

Figure 3: Appearance obtained from the triangular structure with carbon fiber and epoxy resin connections

A manual hydraulic press was used, as shown in Figure 4. A piece of wood was positioned to reach the necessary height so that the press actuator could act. Two metallic plates distributed the tensions in the contact between the wood and the pieces in such a way as to avoid the local plastification of the wood. Two solid metallic rollers, simulating mobile supports, allowing the horizontal displacement of the prototype, as shown in Figure 4.

The displacements presented by the node 1 (upper) of the specimen were noted for each value of applied force. The test took place in two stages. The first consisted of applying force at intervals of 4.45 kN (~0.5 ton) up to a maximum of 26.69 kN (~3 ton), when the first characteristic sounds of brittle rupture were recorded. After that, the specimen was removed from the press for analysis and

inspection, and it was verified that it was still in loading conditions. Then, the second step was performed with the application of force obeying the same slope of charging as said before up to 35.59 kN (~4 ton). The second phase of the experimentation can well represent reload situations typical of maintenance operations.

a) Press and specimen position.

b) Specifications and detailing.

Figure 4: Triangular wooden structure test with carbon fiber

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It is important to point out that the wood was intact before the test, showing no cracks, with only a few knots having been noticed. The state of the specimen after the second stage still conserved its original geometry, as can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Specimen after experimental test

Could be observed that the wooden pieces were still well preserved. The carbon fiber, however, showed significant deformations, regarding all nodes. This shows the restrictions imposed by the carbon fiber compared to the lower nodes and the upper node. It is important to note that due to the constructive aspects, typical of real systems, it is possible that there was some eccentricity in the application of force in the upper node, as well as lateral deviations in the plane of the truss due to the perceived movement during the application of the load.

Table 6 presents the results obtained for the displacements presented by node 1 in the two stages of the test.

Table 6: Relationship force-displacement of the top node

Stage 1			Stage 2			Parameters diagram
F		δ	F		δ	
(kN)	(ton)	(mm)	(kN)	(ton)	(mm)	
4.45	0.5	9.3	4.45	0.5	4.6	
8.90	1.0	12.1	8.90	1.0	6.5	
13.34	1.5	15.9	13.34	1.5	9.1	
17.79	2.0	18.2	17.79	2.0	11.2	
22.24	2.5	20.8	22.24	2.5	13.7	
26.69	3.0	25.8	26.69	3.0	15.3	
F = vertical force			31.14	3.5	19.4	
δ = vertical displacement			35.59	4.0	23.3	

The graphics in Figure 6 show the force-displacement relationship of the upper connection in the two stages of the test.

Figure 6: Force-displacement relationships

The displacements presented by the structure in the second stage of the test were lower than those in the first, denoting that there was an increase in the rigidity of the connection, certainly favored by the accommodation, or grouping, of the carbon fiber. The increase in stiffness was of the order of 18%, which can be verified by the angular coefficient of the trend line equation, in the graphs in Figure 6. Also observing the trend line, it is possible to verify the existence of a linear behavior for the force-displacement relations in both stages of the test.

It was observed that the prototype resembles a structure with semi-rigid connections, corroborating the study by Khelifa et al. (2015) that composite materials contribute to increasing the rigidity of the wood, without the need to increase the dimensions of the section, which preserves the original weight of the structural system.

It is important to record that the fabric adopted in the present study was the bidirectional type, because according to the studies by De La Rosa García et al. (2013) and by Globa et al. (2018), this type of material improves the performance of the structure in the sense of reducing its displacement.

The bicomponent epoxy resin proved to be suitable for the process of bonding the wood to the fiber, requiring surface treatment of the base with regularization and removal of impurities, in line with what was recommended by Jankowski et al. (2010). The resin composes the resistant assembly of the connection together with the fiber, thus contributing to the node stiffness.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the connections of a triangular wooden structure with the bidirectional carbon fiber fabric, with the bicomponent epoxy resin, were analyzed. It was possible to observe:

1. The existence of linear behavior of the force-displacement relationship of the connection.
2. The behavior of the joint is as a semi-rigid connection working with a rotational spring coefficient to be calculated.
3. The increase in stiffness with the application of force because of the grouping the fiber in joints.
4. The good condition of the wood pieces after testing.
5. The preservation of the geometry of the prototype after unloading, although registering lateral deviations.
6. The relative ease of making the nodes of round pieces of wood with carbon fiber, in factory.
7. The suitability of using epoxy resin in bonding carbon fiber to wooden parts can be verified.

The present investigation, of a preliminary nature, led to the conclusion that the carbon fiber associated with the bicomponent epoxy resin proves to be a viable material for the connection of wooden bars in the formation of truss nodes, as it presents ease of handling, assembly speed and structural lightness. The results obtained from the displacements will make it possible to obtain the rotational stiffness coefficient of the connection, allowing the correct attribution of the boundary conditions of the elements of a truss, to evaluate the service limit state within the design scope.

Future studies aim to expand the sampling of prototypes, performing numerical-computational simulations via finite element method to enable evaluation the limit states of design. Additional tests can be conducted to verify conditions of resin absorption by the base material. In addition, an evaluation of how aspects related to the moisture present in the wood, its porosity, moisture content and ambient temperature are capable of interfering in the structural displacement and in the conditions of adhesion of the carbon fiber to the wood.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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